

Resolution and Implicit Effects of Time in Quantum Bound States

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 23, 2019

It is known that the quantum bound state wavefunction may oscillate, both in space and momentum space. The resolution of these oscillations may become greater as energy increases, as in oscillator states. In this note, we examine aspects of linear algebra in a space defined by the unit vectors $\{f_p\}$ where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}=\text{Sum over } p f_p \exp(ipx)$. For high resolution, we argue small changes in p lead to large movements (from one vector to another) in $\{f_p\}$ space and vice versa. Finally, we examine effects of rapid fluctuations in the dot product of $\{f_p\}$ and $\{\exp(px)\}$ where the latter represents single particle motion through space. This affects spatial resolution. Furthermore, as energy increases, the idea of an envelope function becomes relevant. We argue that this is due to an implicit assumption linking high resolution and short time periods. We are not aware of this having been discussed in the literature, although quantum mechanics has historically been described in terms of linear algebra and it is possible that the linear algebra of vectors such as $\{f_p\}$ has been examined.

Orthogonal Wavefunctions

It is well known quantum bound states $W_n(x)$ for a given $V(x)$ (potential) are orthogonal in space. This follows from properties of the time-independent Schrodinger differential equation. A wavefunction $W_n(x)$ may be written as $\text{Sum over } p f_p \exp(ipx)$ with $\text{Sum over } p f_p^* f_p = 1$. Here the sum can be replaced by an integral. Similarly, $\text{Integral } dx W(x)W(x)=1$. Given that different states are orthonormal: $\text{Integral } dx W_n(x)W_m(x)=\delta(n,m)$. This seems to imply that $\text{Sum over } p f_n(p) f_m(p) = \delta(n,m)$. Thus, the set $f_n(p)$ where $n=0,1,2\dots$ to infinity seems to represent a basis in $\{f_p\}$ space and are also points on a unit sphere. The basis set $\{f_p\}$ seems to differ from $\{1, 0, 0,0\dots\}$, $\{0,1,0,0\dots\}$ etc as the f_p can be positive and negative and fluctuate rapidly for high energy. This has an important consequence on dot products and it seems such dot products play an important role in quantum mechanics.

Cycling of the $\{f_p\}$ Vector

The time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((1))$$

may be written in terms of Fourier transforms of both $V(x)$ and $W(x)$. This leads to:

$$\text{Sum over } k V_k f_{p-k} = (E - p^2/2m) f_p \text{ for each } p \quad ((2))$$

Equation ((2)) shows each f_p number is related to a vector $\{f_{p-k}\}$ which combines, through the dot product, with the fixed vector $\{V_k\}$. $\{f_{p-k}\}$ is a permutation of the vector $\{f_p\}$ thus as one moves from one p to another, one permutes the vector $\{f_p\}$ and moves from one point on a sphere in $\{f_p\}$ space to another. One is restricted to a sphere because $\sum_p f_p^2 = 1$. One may imagine this dot product taking values of 0 for particular $\{f_{p-k}\}$ vectors. (Here p is fixed and each element of the vector represents a different k value.) When the dot product becomes 0, ((2)) shows f_p becomes 0 (except for the one case of $E = p^2/2m$). A plot of f_p versus p , however, is directly related to the resolution of p . Thus, if the dot product in ((2)) is zero often as one ranges over p , there is high resolution and vice versa. The question becomes: What is the relationship of high p resolution to the picture of $\{f_p\}$ space?

Consider the vector $\{V_k\}$ in f_p space. $\{f_p\}$ is a vector of infinite dimension, so if one considers $\{V_k\}$ to be a basis vector, there are many (infinite) other orthogonal basis vectors to $\{V_k\}$. A set of basis vectors is given by $f_n(p)$ where n is particular energy level. For example, for the ground state oscillator $f_{p0} = \exp(-bp^2)$ while for higher states $f_{pn} = H_n(p) \exp(-bp^2)$ where $H_n(p)$ is a Hermite polynomial. Thus, the entries of f_{p0} and f_{pn} are different.

For a particular energy level, i.e. a given n , there is a certain amount of fluctuation in elements of $\{f_{p-k}\}$. Thus, if $\{V_k\} \cdot \{f_{p-k}\}$ is 0 for a $\{f_{p-k}\}$ with many fluctuations (like a high frequency $\sin(kx)$), then a permutation of this vector also has many fluctuations and one is not surprised if many of the dot products are 0. The high fluctuating nature of the elements of $\{f_{p-k}\}$ seem to dictate the nature of fluctuations on the dot product as one changes p slightly. Thus, one is in a sense characterizing $\{f_p\}$ space in terms of p resolution, with f_p representing higher energies and more fluctuations of elements in the vector leading to higher resolution.

High p resolution seems to be equivalent to large movements through $\{f_p\}$ (in a sense low resolution in $\{f_p\}$ space). It is actually the difference vector $\{V_k\} - \{f_{p-k}\}$ which is going through large magnitude changes. For low p resolution, the dot product with $\{V_k\}$ changes slowly as one varies p , yet ultimately moves from a peak value in f_p to $f_p=0$. Given that each f_p maps into a vector $\{f_{p-k}\}$, one may ask: How does $d/dp f_p$ map into this $\{f_p\}$ space? It seems changing p a little allows one to move a large distance from the vector $\{f_{p-k}\}$ to the vector $\{f_{p+dp-k}\}$. This seems to imply $d/dp f_p$ should be high which is in keeping with f_p having many zeroes and representing high resolution. It is actually the dot product with $\{V_k\}$ which changes rapidly which matches df_p/dp . In three dimensions, one might start with $\{V_k\}$ along the z -axis and find that small changes of p bring the $\{f_{p-k}\}$ vector rapidly down to the x - y plane. For low resolution, this movement seems to be much slower. A relatively constant dot product with the vector $\{V_k\}$ seems to mean that $\{V_k\} - \{f_{p-k}\}$ (a vector) remains more or less fixed in magnitude, while for high resolution, this difference vector varies rapidly in magnitude.

It seems high resolution is implicitly linked to time. High resolution f_p scenarios seem to be linked with high energy (as in the oscillator case), but it also seems a certain fixed time rate is used when comparing a high resolution f_p graph to a low resolution one for the same p range. One assumes the same time rate for each, so for high resolution, an envelope function makes sense. Not only does one move from f_p zero to another in a short p interval, but the implicit idea is the time interval is also correspondingly short. This idea is perhaps clearer for the case of x

space where one has $dx=v dt$ and dx and dt are closely linked. One has $\exp(iEt)$ for a bound wavefunction which means that the cycle time in ((2)) is $1/E$. For a high resolution, high energy situation, this time is very short, so the one cycles rapidly through the $\{fp-k\}$ vector.

The fact that for high p resolution one spans large ranges of magnitude of the difference vector $\{Vk\} - \{fp-k\}$ space seems to be somehow related to ideas of entropy or information. dfp/dp is a component of the momentum form of Fisher's information. One can see here that changes rapidly for high resolution situations.

Spatial Resolution

The scenario related to spatial resolution seems to be different. In this case, one has zeroes of $W(x)= \text{Sum over } p \text{ } fp \exp(ipx)$. For an even wavefunction, one may write $W(x)= \text{Sum over } p \text{ } fp \cos(px)$ or use $\sin(px)$ for an odd one. This is of the form of a dot product:

$$\{fp\} \text{ dot } \{ \exp(ipx) \} \quad ((3))$$

In this case, however, $\{fp\}$ is not a fixed vector like $\{Vk\}$ in the momentum case discussed above. Different energies and resolutions have different $\{fp\}$ vectors, with different amounts of fluctuation among the vector elements. Given a specific $\{fp\}$, the average kinetic energy is:

$$\text{Sum over } p \text{ } fp*fp \text{ } p^2/2m$$

Also, fp from different states (i.e. $fn(p)$ and $fm(p)$) should be orthogonal vectors on a unit circle in $\{fp\}$ space. Thus, $\{ \exp(ipx) \}$ which is the same for all states and changes as one changes x has more rapid dot product fluctuations with one basis vector than with another. The high dot product fluctuations come from $\{fp\}$ vectors representing high energy and high fluctuations among elements.

The choice of fp not only determines the average kinetic energy, but the manner in which the single particle states $\exp(ipx)$ interfere or are correlated.

For a high x resolution situation, one has many zeroes of $W(x)$ in a certain span of x . The vector $\{ \exp(ipx) \}$ represents the evolution of different momentum plane waves under the influence of no force. Linking them with a dot product with $\{fp\}$ creates correlated motion. It seems there is again an important notion of implicit time. One has $dx=v dt$ for a tiny interval, so small dx intervals are automatically associated with small times. Thus, for high x resolution, one has zeroes of $W(x)$ in short dx intervals and hence in short dt intervals. The idea of an envelope function makes sense for the high resolution case as one is in a sense ignoring the changes in $W(x)$ as it moves from a peak to the next peak. This is taken to happen very rapidly, and so the details may be ignored so to speak. If one does not assume a small dt associated with a small dx , then it may take a very large time to move from a peak value of $W(x)$ to $W(x)=0$ even if the x

difference from the peak to the zero is small. In such a case, it is not clear why one would use an envelope function as the “details” are important. This seems also seems to be related to the uncertainty principle. If E is large and resolution is large, then dt is assumed to be small as one moves from one peak to another.

Linking Momentum and Spatial Resolution

If one tries to link momentum and spatial resolution, it seems one has:

$$\left\{ \left[\sum_k V_k \psi_{p-k} \right] / \left[E - p^2/2m \right] \right\} \cdot \left\{ \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((4))$$

For high p resolution, the vectors $\{ \psi_{p-k} \}$ and $\{ \psi_{p+dp-k} \}$ are far apart in $\{ \psi_p \}$ space (i.e. the difference vector has a large magnitude) and so it seems are perhaps not much correlated. Thus, $\left[\sum_k V_k \psi_{p-k} \right]$ is able to fluctuate rapidly as one moves from one p value to another in the vector $\{ \psi_p \}$. For low resolution, the vectors are close and correlated and the terms in $\{ \psi_p \}$ do not change as rapidly. Thus, in such a case most changes in the dot product in ((4)) come from the single particle changes $\exp(ipx)$. It seems these change slowly as the x resolution is low. For a $W(x)$ with high x resolution one needs a high $d/dx W(x)$ which implies high ψ_p for high p values from Fourier analysis. It seems that by having $\left[\sum_k V_k \psi_{p-k} \right]$ fluctuate rapidly with p one can obtain high weights for some high p . For slow variations of $\left[\sum_k V_k \psi_{p-k} \right]$, one might have uniform damping of high ψ_p .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that it seems one may consider bound quantum states and issues of resolution by considering linear algebra in $\{ \psi_p \}$ space, both for p and x . In the case of momentum, one chooses a fixed vector $\{ V_k \}$, where V_k is the Fourier transform of $V(x)$ and performs permutations of $\{ \psi_{p-k} \}$. For high p resolution, the elements of $\{ \psi_p \}$ fluctuate rapidly and lead to rapidly fluctuating dot products. They also produce difference vectors $\{ V_k \} - \{ \psi_{p-k} \}$ with a large range of magnitudes with small changes in p yielding many $\psi_p=0$ points. In the case of x , one does not have such a fixed vector. One considers the vector of single particle motion $\{ \exp(ipx) \}$ and its dot product with various $\{ \psi_p \}$ vectors. If the dot product varies rapidly with changes in x , one has high x resolution. (This seems to happen for $\{ \psi_p \}$ with highly fluctuating elements.) This high x resolution seems to be associated with short time periods as one assumes implicitly that $dx=vdt$. This allows for the notion of an envelope function for very high resolution $W(x)$ and seems to be related to the energy-time uncertainty principle as high energy and short time are linked.